

A Study on Metal Chelates of Substituted Hydroxyphenylpyrazoles with some Bivalent Transition Metal Ions

B. ANANDAM^a and P. LINGAIAH^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, C. K. M. Arts and Science College, Warangal-506 009

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 2 September 1991, revised 1 September 1992, accepted 17 September 1992

The stability constants of metal chelates of substituted hydroxyphenylpyrazoles, viz. 3(5)-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5(3)-phenylpyrazole (OHPPPz), 3(5)-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5(3)-(4-chlorophenyl)pyrazole (OHPCPPz) and 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,5-diphenylpyrazole (OHPDPPz) with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO₂^{II} have been evaluated pH-metrically in solutions of varying dielectric constant, ionic strength and at different temperature, using Bjerrum's method as adopted by Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants of the bivalent metal chelates with all the ligands follow the order: Cd < Zn < Co < Ni < Cu < UO₂. The effect of substituents of the ligands in the complex formation has also been studied.

In continuation of earlier work¹ on ionisation constants of hydroxyphenylpyrazoles, we report here the stability constants of metal chelates of 3(5)-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5(3)-phenylpyrazole (OHPPPz), 3(5)-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5(3)-(4-chlorophenyl)pyrazole (OHPCPPz) and 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,5-diphenylpyrazole (OHPDPPz) with bivalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and UO₂ determined in methanol-water medium as a function of ionic strength, temperature and dielectric constant.

Results and Discussion

3-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)pyrazole acts as a bidentate ligand coordinating through tertiary nitrogen and phenolic oxygen to form six-membered ring. From the titration curves of (i), (ii) and (iii), the value of \bar{n} and pL were evaluated using Irving and Rossotti method. The formation curves were constructed by plotting \bar{n} vs pL. The formation curves obtained for all metal complexes under investigation showed the maximum \bar{n} at 2.0, indicating the formation of 1:2 metal complexes in solution. The values of log K₁ and log K₂ were corrected using least-square method (Table 1).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF OHPPPz, OHPCPPz AND OHPDPPz WITH METAL IONS

Temp. = 35°, solvent: MeOH-H₂O (60:40, v/v), $\mu = 0.1$ M (KNO₃)

Metal(II) ion	OHPPPz		OHPCPPz		OHPDPPz	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
Co	5.68	5.44	5.20	4.74	8.18	6.24
Ni	7.16	7.12	6.67	5.68	8.80	7.25
Cu	8.27	7.84	7.93	7.57	9.40	7.40
Zn	6.18	5.97	5.95	5.08	8.69	7.15
Cd	5.92	4.98	5.54	4.80	8.24	6.60
UO ₂	8.38	7.82	8.26	7.55	9.60	9.00

The ligands OHPDPPz, OHPPPz and OHPCPPz (HL) may react with metal ion M²⁺ in one of the following ways.

(I) Direct interaction of the ligand with the metal ion:

(II) Ionisation of the ligand followed by complexation:

In order to find out the nature of interaction between the metal ion and the ligand, the stability constants of OHPDPPz, OHPPPz and OHPCPPz with Co^{II} ion were determined at different ionic strengths in the range 0.02–0.1 M (KNO₃) in 60% (v/v) methanol-water mixture at 35°. The log K values of the metal chelate are related to the ionic strength of the medium by the extended form of the Debye-Hückel equation,

$$\log K = \log K_0 + \frac{A \Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$$

ΔZ^2 values were calculated from the slopes of the plots of log K against $\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu})$ (Fig. 1). For the log K₁ these values were found to be in the range of –2.1 to –2.16 suggesting that the first stage of complexation proceeds through the mechanism shown in equation (Ia). The ΔZ^2 values calculated (1.87 to –2.08) for the second stage of complexation are close to the theoretical value (–2.0), indicating that complexation takes place as per equation (IIb). Therefore, the overall reaction can be represented

as

The formation constants of the metal chelates of OHPDPPz, OHPPPz and OHPCPPz with Co^{II} were determined in solutions of different dielectric constants. The dielectric constant of the medium was varied by varying the percentage of methanol. The plots of log *K* vs 1/*D* of the medium are linear with positive slopes suggesting that log *K* increases with increase in the proportion of organic component. Using the Amis equation,

$$\log K = \log K_0 - \frac{Z_A Z_B e^2}{2.303 r_0 K T} \times 1/D$$

the distance of closest approach (*r*₀) was calculated as (1.2 and 2.6 Å) for the 2nd stage of complexation reaction of the metal complexes of Co^{II} with OHPPPz and OHPCPPz.

The Arrhenius plots (log *K* vs 1/*T*) were drawn for the complexes of OHPDPPz, OHPPPz and OHPCPPz with Co^{II} at different temperatures in the range 15–34° in 60% (v/v) methanol-water mixture at 0.1 *M* ionic strength (KNO₃). From the slopes, the thermodynamic parameters were evaluated (Table 2). The negative ΔS values observed during the formation of the complexes show loss of entropy indicating that the complexes are more polar than the reactants and hence strongly solvated.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Co^{II} COMPLEXES WITH OHPPPz, OHPCPPz AND OHPDPPz

Solvent: MeOH-H ₂ O (60:40, v/v), $\mu=0.1$ M (KNO ₃)			
	$-\Delta H$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S$ J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
OHPPPz:			
log <i>K</i> ₁	153.17	33.47	388.61
log <i>K</i> ₂	102.05	32.05	227.23
OHPCPPz:			
log <i>K</i> ₁	134.00	30.67	335.51
log <i>K</i> ₂	86.15	27.95	188.95
OHPDPPz:			
log <i>K</i> ₁	109.37	48.24	198.57
log <i>K</i> ₂	84.22	36.77	154.02

An attempt was also made to calculate the isokinetic temperature (*B*^{*}) for the complexation reactions. Exner has evaluated the *B*^{*} values from the plots of log *K*_{T₁} vs log *K*_{T₂}. In the present study the plot of log *K*_{308K} vs log *K*_{318K} (Fig. 1) is linear. From the slope (b) the isokinetic temperature is calculated using the equation,

$$\beta = \frac{T_1 T_2 (b-1)}{b T_2 - T_1}$$

The value thus obtained (330 K) is in good agreement with that obtained from the plot (Fig. 1) of

ΔH vs ΔS (335 K) and is above the experimental temperature (308–318 K) indicating that the complexation reactions are enthalpy controlled².

Fig 1 (A) Plot of log *K* of Co^{II} complex of OHPPPz vs $1/\mu/1 + \mu$ (1, 2, 3), (B) (4) plot of ΔH vs ΔS , (5) plot of log *K*₃₀₈ vs log *K*₃₁₈ for different metal ligand systems

The stability constants of the metal chelates of bivalent metal ions with all the ligands follow the Irving-William's order, viz. Cd^{II} < Zn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} < UO₂. The plot of log *K* vs p*K*_a of the ligands is linear, illustrating a graphical relationship between the basicities of the ligands and their ability to undergo complexation with different metal ions. The slope obtained in all the cases is less than unity, indicating that the effect of substituent of the ligand on the stability of the complex is almost negligible³.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared by the reported method⁴. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc and their m.p.s. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Metal nitrates were dissolved in CO₂-free double-distilled water and standardised⁵.

An Elico LI-120 pH-meter with combined glass and calomel electrode was used. The volume and the pH-corrections in solutions of various aquo-organic mixtures were made as suggested by Rao and Mathur⁶ and Van Uitert and Haas⁷ respectively. The experimental method consists of pH-metric titrations of (i) nitric acid, (ii) nitric acid+ligand and (iii) nitric acid+ligand+metal ion, against standard sodium hydroxide.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.A.M.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the financial assistance.

References

1. B. ANANDAM, A. K. MURTHY and P. LINGAIAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, communicated.
2. A. WEISBERGER, "Techniques of Organic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1961, Vol. III, Part I, p. 207.
3. Z. L. ERNST and MEERNASHI, *J. Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 2838.
4. T. C. SHARMA, V. SAXENA and N. J. REDDY, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1977, **93**, 415; T. C. SHARMA, S. R. PAWAR and N. J. REDDY, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1983, **111**, 159.
5. A. L. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1964.
6. U. B. RAO and H. B. MATHUR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 2919.
7. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.